

Challenges encountered by Women IT Professionals: An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT

In the IT industry, women are enrolling in large numbers, driven by the vast opportunities available. Women are often Multitaskers, a skill they typically excel in compared to men those in the IT sector, frequently face persistent challenges, especially in balancing their professional responsibilities with societal expectations. This article focuses on analyzing the various challenges encountered by working women professionals in the IT sector. In this study, 15 Challenges were highlighted, and data were obtained from the women IT professionals working in various IT organizations. The study was undertaken in and around Bengaluru City. The study was conducted using primary data collected through Google Forms. The study sample size was 113 respondents. The information is garnered from different age groups and income levels of the respondents. Among all the Challenges 'lack of flexible work options' was ranked '1st', 'Work-Life equilibrium' was ranked '2nd', 'Under appreciation' was ranked '3rd' with a, and 'Under representation in leadership positions' was ranked 13th, 'Workplace harassment' was ranked 14th, 'Confidence gap' was ranked '15th' using Z test proportion based on the respondents' experiences with these challenges.

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I. Introduction:

The IT sector has a universal appeal, due to its wide range of innovations, constant growth, and transformative impact on modern society. In India, a significant number of students aim for a career in the IT sector because of the multitude of options available, the handsome pay, and the social recognition enjoyed in the field. The percentage of women entering the IT sector has improved significantly because of the convenience of office-based roles compared to fieldwork, combined with attractive salary packages and career growth opportunities. Married women, especially those in dual-career households, face unique challenges in balancing professional and personal lives, making it more difficult to satisfy the demands of work and personal life. It is crucial to concentrate on the various challenges women face and identify the most vital concerns that require focus, enabling effective strategies to address and overcome these difficulties. Unless organizations focus on understanding the challenges faced by women, it will be hard to extract quality work, as their role has prominence in both the workplace and their home. This paper highlights the challenges faced by women IT professionals.

Objective of the Study:

To analyze the various challenges faced by working women employees in IT sector.

II. Review of Literature:

Mittal, Sharma, and Srivastava's (2015) paper titled "Challenges faced by working women at workplace, family, and society—its major issues, impact, and remedial measures." examines the Polymorphic challenges faced by working women, particularly in the workplace, family, and society. It concentrated on problems like gender bias, wage gaps, and the dual burden of career and household responsibilities, which often lead to stress and other mental issues. The authors propose remedial measures such as workplace reforms, flexible working hours, and societal shifts towards shared caregiving responsibilities. Overall, the paper provides valuable insights into the problems women face and promotes systemic changes to encourage gender equality and improve women's well-being in both professional and personal spheres.

Rashid, Mohammad, and Mahejabin's (2023), paper titled "Women at work: Exploring challenges confronting women in professional environments". This study explores the specific challenges that women in IT face, particularly the gender discrimination that often sidelines their contributions and inhibits career growth. The article highlights the gender imbalance within tech

organizations, where women are underrepresented in leadership positions, which further impacts their visibility and access to opportunities. The authors also discuss the difficulty in work-life balance, with many women having to endure the pressures of family commitments alongside demanding careers in IT. Their research reinforces the need for more inclusive policies and workplace cultures that not only recognize the value women bring to the industry but also provide tangible support systems to enable their success.

III. Research Methodology:

In this study, Challenges faced by women in Information Technology had been analyzed and data had been obtained from the employees in Bengaluru city.

- **Sources of Data:** The data was collected by primary data collected by Google forms.
- **Sampling Technique:** The sampling method used for the study is Convenience Sampling.
- **Sample Size:** The sampling size taken for the study is from 113 Respondents.
- **Statistical Tools Used:** The following statistical tools have been used to examine primary data collected.
 - a) Percentage Analysis
 - b) Z-test for proportions

IV. FINDINGS & DISCUSSIONS:

1. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS:

The following table represents the demographic profile of the respondents by using simple percentage analysis:

Table -1 Demographic Profile Of The Respondents			
Factors	Classifications	N	Percentage
Age (in years)	Below 25	38	33.63
	25-35	45	39.82
	36-45	23	20.35
	Above 45	7	6.19

Marital Status	Single	55	48.67
	Married	39	34.51
	Divorced	19	16.81
	Widowed	0	0.00
Educational qualification	Diploma	11	9.73
	Undergraduate	62	54.87
	Postgraduate	40	35.40
Monthly income	Up to 15,000	15	13.27
	Rs.15001 to 25,000	28	24.78
	Rs.25001 to 40,000	32	28.32
	Above 40000	38	33.63
Household arrangement	Residing Independently	24	21.24
	Sharing a residence with roommates	25	22.12
	Living with spouse	30	26.55
	Residing with spouse's family	9	7.96
	Living with parents/ immediate family members	25	22.12

Interpretation:

The above table shows that 39.82 per cent of the respondents belong to the age group of 25-35 years, 48.67 percent of the respondents are single, 54.87 percent of the respondents are undergraduate, 33.63 per cent of the respondents' income is Above 40,000 and 26.55 per cent of the respondents are living with spouse.

2. CURRENT POSITION OF THE RESPONDENTS:

The following table represents the current position of the respondents in their organization:

Table 2: Current Position of the Respondents		
Designation	No of Respondents	Percentage

Junior Level	44	38.93
Senior Level	38	33.62
Associate level	21	18.58
Executive level	10	8.84
Total	113	100

Interpretation:

The above table depicts that 38.93 per cent of the respondents are working in junior level, 33.62 per cent of the respondents are working in senior level, 21 per cent of the respondents are working in associate level and 10 per cent of the respondents are working in Executive level.

3. WORKING EXPERIENCE IN IT SECTORS:

The following table represents the working experience of the respondents in the IT sector:

Table – 3: Respondents’ Working Experience In IT Sector		
Working Experience	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 5 years	45	39.82
5 to 10 years	38	33.62
Above 10 years	30	26.54
Total	113	100

(Source: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table 3, it is inferred that 39.82 percent of respondents have below 5 years working experience in IT sector, 33.62 percent of the respondents have 5 to 10 years working experience in the IT sector, and 26.54 percent of respondents have above 10 years' experience in IT sector.

4. CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN IT PROFESSIONALS - Z-TEST FOR PROPORTIONS

The following table represents the various challenges encountered by women IT professionals and based on their opinions on these challenges , given the rankings based on Z-score:

Table -5: Ranking the Challenges faced By Women IT Professionals using Z -test proportions

S. No	Challenges faced by women IT professionals	'Yes' responses	Proportion	S.D	Z-score	Rank
1	Gender Favoritism	54	0.4778761	0.0679 75	-0.343	8 th
2	Compensation disparity	61	0.539823	0.0638 15	0.619	7 th
3	Workplace harassment	22	0.1946903	0.0844 19	-3.64	14 th
4	Confidence gap	21	0.1858407	0.0848 82	-3.75	15 th
5	Insufficient networking exposure	53	0.4690265	0.0685 48	-0.469	9 th
6	Under appreciation	68	0.6017699	0.0593 65	1.71	3 rd
7	Work-Life Equilibrium	69	0.6106195	0.0587 01	1.9	2 nd
8	Prolonged work hours/days	63	0.5575221	0.0625 76	0.92	5 th
9	Conservative work culture	38	0.3362832	0.0766 39	-2.16	11 th
10	Career advancement opportunities	51	0.4513274	0.0696 81	-0.71	10 th
11	Limited exposure to top profile projects	62	0.5486726	0.0631 98	0.76	6 th
12	Challenges in professional renewal	35	0.3097345	0.0781 57	-2.45	12 th
13	Underrepresentation in leadership positions	23	0.2035398	0.0839 54	-3.58	13 th
14	Lack of flexible work options	72	0.6371681	0.0566	2.45	1 st

				65		
15	Physical and mental health issues	65	0.5752212	0.0613 12	1.23	4 th

(Source: Primary data)

Interpretation:

The table above shows that among 113 respondents, 72 respondents stated that “lack of flexible work options” is the biggest challenge they face. As a result, it was ranked 1st with the highest Z-score of 2.45. 69 respondents expressed that “work-life equilibrium” is the second biggest challenge, ranking it 2nd with a Z-score of 1.9. Similarly, 68 respondents identified “underappreciation” as the third biggest challenge, ranking it 3rd with a Z-score of 1.71.

On the other hand, 23 respondents considered “underrepresentation in leadership positions” as one of the least significant challenges, ranking it 13th with a Z-score of -3.58. 22 respondents identified “workplace harassment” as the second least significant factor, placing it at 14th rank with a Z-score of -3.64. Finally, 21 respondents cited “confidence gap” as the least significant factor, ranking it 15th with the lowest Z-score of -3.75.

V. CONCLUSION:

This study highlighted the various challenges faced by women professionals in the Information Technology sector, and asked them to rank the challenges they faced, a total of 113 respondents of the convenience sample shared their experience with these challenges and these challenges are ranked by using the Z test for proportions method. 'lack of flexible work options' was ranked '1st 'with a Z score of 2.45, 'Work-Life equilibrium' was ranked '2nd ' with a Z score of 1.9, 'Under appreciation' was ranked '3rd 'with a Z score of 1.71and 'Underrepresentation in leadership positions' was ranked 13th with a z score of -3.58, 'Workplace harassment' was ranked 14th with a z score of -3.64, 'Confidence gap' was ranked '15th ' with a least Z score of -3.75 based on the information collected from the respondents. These challenges, along with gender-based discrimination and pay inequality, point to broader systemic issues that obstruct women's professional growth and well-being in the IT industry. Addressing these challenges through policy reforms, better support systems and a more inclusive and flexible workplace can help create an environment where women can

grow in both professional and personal spheres. The organizations must prioritize these issues to encourage gender parity and empower women to reach their full potential in the tech field.

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